

Seed setting on 2 cytosterile lines in relation to direction and distance from the pollen source. IRRI, 1980 dry season.

Direction	Seed set (%)					Mean (%)
	30 cm	50 cm	70 cm	90 cm	110 cm	
<i>Cytosterile Zhen Shan 97A</i>						
Southwest	28.2	24.9	19.5	17.1	22.0	22.3
Southeast	21.3	11.5	4.5	6.0	3.6	9.4
Northwest	16.8	1.3	4.1	6.9	4.1	8.0
Northeast	3.9	1.6	1.4	0.6	1.1	1.7
Mean	17.6	11.3	7.5	1.6	7.7	10.4
<i>Cytosterile V20A</i>						
Southwest	19.0	10.1	11.9	11.7	9.1	12.4
Southeast	19.9	7.3	8.0	11.2	10.0	11.3
Northwest	8.9	8.9	4.6	2.5	2.9	5.6
Northeast	8.6	3.2	1.2	0.9	1.0	3.0
Mean	14.1	7.4	6.4	6.6	5.8	8.1

open for natural outcrossing. The extent of outcrossing on the male sterile plants, located at various distances from the pollen source, was determined by comparing the seed set on two randomly selected, unbagged panicles with that on bagged panicles. The data were adjusted in relation to percentage seed set of the pollen sources (94.4% for Zhen Shan 97B and 86.3% for V20B).

The two cytosterile lines did not set any seed on the bagged panicles. This

indicated the stability of their male sterility system. Seed set on the open pollinated panicles varied with the cytosterile line, direction of planting, and distance in relation to the pollinator (see table). Some individual plants gave as high as 35-45% seed set. Cytosterile Zhen Shan 97A showed higher seed set than V20A, probably because of its slightly better panicle exertion and synchronized flowering in relation to the pollen source. The higher seed set on the

male sterile plants located in southwest and southeast directions than on the plants located in the other two directions may have been caused by the prevailing wind direction (mostly north-northeast) during the flowering period (18 Feb - 16 Mar). Seed set was higher on plants 30 cm away from the pollen source than on plants located further away. The effect of distance up to 110 cm on natural outcrossing was, however, less pronounced on the plot in the southwest, which lay across the direction of wind. Therefore, it should be possible to obtain satisfactory seed set in hybrid seed production plots by growing five rows of a cytosterile line (1-m wide strip) alternately with one row of pollen source.

Although we did not practice manual flag leaf clipping and supplemental pollination, as in China, the results are encouraging. Further increase in natural outcrossing on rice cytosterile lines should be possible through selection or breeding, or both, of male sterile lines possessing shorter flag leaves, well-exserted panicles, and spikelets with exserted stigma. ■

Genetic composition of parents used in crosses and of subsequent rice varieties

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Plant breeders develop most improved crop varieties by hybridization or crossbreeding. In 1975, IRRI began a study of Asian plant breeders' use of semidwarf rice varieties as parents in their crosses. The data were collected at 14 research centers: 7 centers in India, 2 in Korea, and 1 each in Bangladesh, Indonesia, the Philippines, Sri Lanka, and Thailand.

We speculated that *cross analysis* might be used as a tool in predicting the genetic composition of future crop varieties. We compared data on rice cultivars that Asian plant breeders crossed over a 10-year period (1965-75) with data on the genetic composition of the improved rice varieties released and recommended to farmers 5 years

Comparison of use of varieties as parents in crosses and genetic composition of improved rice varieties released from 1965-80. 355 randomly selected crosses involving 819 parents at 7 research centers and 202 varieties involving 433 parents. IRRI, 1980.

later (1975-1980) in the same countries. Five or six years is about the minimum time required to advance the progeny of a cross to the varietal stage.

In 1980, a list of 202 improved rice varieties, developed locally and released in the 7 Asian countries, was compiled from records of the IRRI-sponsored

International Rice Genetic Survey. Copies of the lists were sent to the senior rice breeder of each research center, with the request that he provide each variety's cross, and add new varieties not recorded and the year of release.

We then plotted the percentages of new varieties that were progeny of major gene sources released from 1965 to 1970, from 1971 to 1975, and from 1976 to 1980.

The most heavily used semidwarf parents in crosses were Taichung Native 1 (TN1) and IR8. The other semidwarf parents were categorized as *locally developed* (bred by the national

programs); *other IRRI* (any IRRI cultivar other than IR 8); and *introduced from another country* (for example if Sona, an Indian semidwarf, were used in Indonesian crosses).

TN1 was used in 22% of all the crosses analyzed for 1965-67, and appeared as a parent of 40% of the new varieties released in the same nations by 1970 (see figure). The steady decline in its use as a parent in the subsequent decade was matched by a corresponding decline in its appearance as a direct parent of new varieties released.

IR8 was involved in about 20% of the crosses made in the mid-1960s and was

a parent of about 25% of the varieties released 5 or 6 years later. Its use in crosses increased and then declined; so did its subsequent appearance as a parent of varieties. Breeders had almost stopped using IR8 as a parent by 1975, but it was a parent of 24% of the varieties released from that time until 1980.

The strongest trend found in the 1975 survey was the increasing use of locally developed semidwarfs as parents—from 0 to about 50% from 1965 to 1975. But of the subsequent varieties, only about 20% are progeny of those crosses. Most of the local semidwarf parents were progeny of IR8 or TN1. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Sheath rot incidence and chaffy grain percentage on some popular rices

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The incidence of sheath rot of rice and percentage of resulting chaffiness on some popular varieties grown in the Chhattisgarh region of MP in 1979

kharif were recorded. Nine varieties were grown in a replicated trial with fertilizer applied at 60-40-20 kg NPK/ha with 3 replications/variety.

The disease incidence was assessed by observing for sheath rot symptoms 10 plants from 3 patches selected for each replication. The percentage of infection was calculated by counting the infected and healthy panicles for each plant (see table).

The infected panicles that showed sheath rot symptoms were randomly collected from the plots and pooled. Because neck rot infection also increases chaffy grain production, care was taken to select neck rot-free panicles. The chaffy and filled grains of 10 panicles were counted. The healthy panicles with no sheath rot or neck rot served as control. The percentage of chaffy grains was higher in the diseased panicles than in the healthy ones.

Percentage of sheath rot incidence and chaffy grains developed. Madhya Pradesh, India.

Variety	Panicle infection (%)	Chaffy grains (%) on	
		Diseased panicles	Healthy panicles
Phakuna	28.8	31.0	8.2
Madhuri	31.2	49.5	9.4
Anupama	32.0	45.8	8.9
Jaya	37.2	32.6	7.5
Kranti	38.0	37.5	11.5
Patel 85	49.5	38.0	12.0
Pragati	53.2	42.0	10.5
Bangoli 5	62.7	30.1	11.0
Patel 17	72.5	48.0	15.0

Patel 17 had maximum incidence and Phalguna minimum. Bangoli 5 had more infection than Phalguna, but the latter had a higher percentage of chaffiness.

Similar observations were made on Patel 17 and Anupama. This indicates that the time of panicle infection may play an important role in chaffy grain production. ■

Outbreak of sheath rot on rice

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During late kharif 1978-79, an outbreak of sheath rot (caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae*) occurred at Nellore. In October, entries in the national screening nursery were planted singly in 2 rows, each 3 m long. A spacing of 20 x 15 cm was adopted. Urea at 150 kg N/ha was applied in 3 equal splits. Sheath rot was observed at the panicle initiation stage. Unusual rains in December (153 mm), in addition to cool moist weather with

relative humidity of 95% and above on many days, helped spread the disease.

The rot appeared on the uppermost leaf sheaths enclosing the young panicles. Oblong lesions on the leaf sheath coalesced quickly and covered most of the sheath. Among 673 entries tested, 124 recorded clear susceptible reactions (score 5-9). In these susceptible entries almost every panicle was damaged by the fungus. Panicles either remained within the leaf sheath or emerged only partially. Young panicles rotted completely. Profuse powdery growth of the fungus was found inside affected leaf sheaths.